

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MULBERRY LEAF

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Abstract

The nutritional value of mulberry leaves depends on a number of agro-climatic conditions, and any deficiency of nutrients in the leaves reduces the ability of the silkworm to produce high-quality silk. A food rich in leaves with a high nutrient content is necessary for the best growth and development of silkworm caterpillars, as well as for the production of high-quality cocoons. To study the valuable properties of mulberry leaves, comprehensive studies of the leaves of common and new varieties of Hasak, Jar Arik-8, SANIISH- 34 Sha-tut were conducted. Determination of the content of ascorbic acid, carotene, organic acids. Knowing the quantitative content of these substances in the leaves, in order to improve the quality and quantity of silk, mulberry leaves are processed with various nutrients to feed the silkworm. In research in the field of sericulture, the enrichment and addition of nutrients to the diet in mulberry leaves are relatively new methods.

Keywords: mulberry, mulberry leaf, chemical composition, flavanol organic acids, ascorbic acid, antimicrobial action

Introduction

Mulberry or mulberry is a valuable plant that is a source of raw materials for many industries. Mulberry leaves are the main food for the silkworm, from the cocoons of which natural silk is produced. Mulberry wood is used in the production of musical instruments. Mulberry is a plant of the mulberry family, a deciduous tree with regular, simple, lobed serrated leaves along the edge. The flowers are sessile, with ears in the form of sinuses, resemble blackberry berries. They appear in May-June, they are barely noticeable in the dense foliage. The fruit is complex, fleshy, white, red or dark purple in color, has a pleasant, fragrant smell and sweet taste.

Sericulture is a well-known, main branch of agriculture. It involves breeding silkworms in order to produce raw silk, which is a yarn unwound from cocoons curled by silkworm caterpillars. The main tasks of sericulture include the cultivation of mulberries for feeding silkworm, production, feeding of caterpillars, primary processing of cocoons, unwinding and spinning of cocoon raw materials, processing of raw silk and weaving.

The silkworm is a monophage. He eats only mulberry leaves due to the presence of the chemical compound Morin (flavonol) in them [1]. The nutritional value of mulberry leaves has a significant impact on the growth and development of larvae, as well as on the subsequent curling of cocoons. By increasing the marketable qualities of the silkworm, nutrition plays a crucial role in sericulture. Mulberry leaf provides almost all the nutrients necessary for the growth of the silkworm-monophage. The only plant used as food is mulberry (*Morus alba* and its types), which is crucial for the development of the silkworm and, ultimately, for

the production and productivity of silk. The quantity and quality of the leaves influence the growth and development of the silkworm, as well as the quantity and quality of cocoons and raw silk produced. The protein of mulberry leaves, which is of the highest quality for the successful production of cocoons, is about 70% of the silk protein produced by the silkworm [2].

The most recent methods in sericulture research include the addition or enrichment of mulberry leaves with various preparations. Studies are being conducted to determine the effect of enrichment with nutritional supplements, including the addition of proteins, carbohydrates, amino acids, vitamins, sterols, hormones, antibiotics and others, to improve productivity and increase productivity, quantity and quality of cocoons. Feeding silkworms with leaves enriched with nutrients improved their growth and development, as well as the economic qualities of cocoons. Numerous compounds, including vitamins, minerals, amino acids, soy protein, hormones and plant extracts, when added to mulberry leaves as additives, improve the characteristics of the cocoon, including the reproductive ability of the silkworm [3,4,5]. In recent years, several initiatives have been taken to enrich mulberry leaves with various useful elements and combinations of nutrients to improve the quality of the cocoon harvest [6,7,8].

Methodology

In order to study the valuable properties of mulberry leaves, comprehensive studies of the leaves of the common varieties Hasak, Jar Arik-8, SANIISH- 34 Sha-tut, which are in the collection of the Research Institute of Sericulture, were conducted.

The content of ascorbic acid was determined, which was determined by the phases of vegetation. The

determination of ascorbic acid content in plants was determined by the method of K. Murri. The method is based on the conversion of ascorbic acid into a solution and on its ability to restore in an acidic environment, the blue indicator – 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenolate sodium – to leucoform, while ascorbic acid is oxidized to dehydroascorbic acid. The reaction is due to the enzyme ascorbate oxidase [9].

The determination of carotene was carried out by the method of mulberry leaves first washed, cleaned, and then crushed on a grater. Take a 1,0 g weight, transfer it to a mortar without loss and grind it with quartz sand. Then 10ml of gasoline is poured into the mortar and continue to grind for several minutes. The mixture is infused for 15 minutes to extract carotene [10].

Extraction of organic acids from plants was carried out with distilled water when heated. The organic acids extracted in this way and filtered are taken into account by titration with 0,1 n. alkali solution. The results of the determinations are recalculated for malic acid, multiplying the amount of 0,1n. NaOH, which went to neutralization by a coefficient of 0,0067. The content of organic acids is expressed in mg per 100g of plant material [11].

Research results

Proteins and carbohydrates are most important for the formation of silk. However, for the digestibility of proteins and to increase the viability of the silkworm, the feed must contain a certain amount of mineral salts. The optimal nutritional value is possessed by leaves that have spring feeding in absolutely dry matter by the period of the fifth age of caterpillars; nitrogen - 3,5%-4%, soluble carbohydrates - 7-9, potassium - 1,6-2,0, calcium-2,5-3 and phosphorus-0,2-0,3%.

The chemical composition of the leaves depends on the variety, age, type of formation, lighting and agrotechnical care. High nutritional value is characteristic of the leaves of high-altitude Central Asian varieties, from feeding which large cocoons are obtained.

The chemical difference in quality is related not only to the variety, but also to the sex of plants.

A leaf of a certain quality must correspond to each cycle of development of silkworm caterpillars, therefore, the timing of the revival of caterpillars, the selection of mulberry varieties, watering and fertilization are regulated.

The results for determining the content of ascorbic acid in mulberry leaves are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Ascorbic acid content in mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	Vegetation phase	Ascorbic acid content, mg per absolutely dry weight				
		Leaf blade	Petioles	Young leaf	Old leaf	twigs
Hasak mulberry	Blossom	1043	-	-	-	-
	Fruiting	1180	335	1180	1007	501
	Ripening of berries	500	50	501	300	100
	After removing the berries	320	30	400	200	70
Jar arik -8	Blossom	800	-	-	-	-
	Fruiting	880	160	712	754	375
	Ripening of berries	400	40	380	200	40
	After removing the berries	280	20	250	130	20
SANIISH-34	Blossom	960	-	-	-	-
	Fruiting	880	320	712	754	275
	Ripening of berries	450	40	450	250	60
	After removing the berries	300	30	280	130	20
Sha-tut mulberry	Blossom	1050	-	-	-	-
	Fruiting	1200	400	1250	1100	700
	Ripening of berries	600	100	700	300	200
	After removing the berries	350	50	600	200	100

Thus, when young leaves appear, there is a low content of ascorbic acid, which increases by the time of flowering and continues to accumulate, reaching a maximum by the time the berries are tied.

The content of carotene in mulberry leaves was determined, the results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Carotene content in mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	Carotene content in leaves, mg per absolutely dry weight			
	Blossom	Fruiting	Ripening of berries	After removing the berries
Hasak mulberry	13,3	34,8	36,1	34,1
Jar arik- -8	14,5	33,7	34,1	32,5
SANIISH-34	8,2	36,7	37,2	27,5
Sha-tut mulberry	15,2	38,7	39,2	34,5

So the carotene content in the leaves of the studied varieties increases after the beginning of flowering reaches a maximum when the berries ripen, then the carotene content drops. The highest content of carotene was noted in the Sha-tut variety.

The content of organic acids in mulberry leaves of the studied varieties in different phases of vegetation was also determined. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Content of organic acids in mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	Vegetation phase	Organic acid content, % by absolutely dry weight			
		Volatile	Sum of acids	Titrated	Related
Hasak mulberry	Blossom	0,2	2,47	1,9	0,57
	Fruiting	0,57	2,61	1,54	1,07
	Ripening of berries	0,4	2,2	1,3	0,9
SANIISH-34	Blossom	1,16	4,08	2,4	1,68
	Fruiting	1,05	2,68	1,33	1,35
	Ripening of berries	0,53	2,18	1,05	1,13
Jar arik-8	Blossom	1,18	5,36	2,88	2,48
	Fruiting	0,61	2,71	1,54	1,17
	Ripening of berries	0,33	2,51	1,40	1,11
Sha-tut mulberry	Blossom	0,22	5,50	2,91	2,49
	Fruiting	1,15	2,78	1,55	1,23
	Ripening of berries	0,61	2,59	1,45	1,14

The highest content of organic acids was noted in the leaves of the studied varieties during the flowering period of mulberry, then the acid content drops sharply.

Further, a study was conducted to determine the presence of some organic acids in the leaves of the studied varieties, their results are shown in Table 4

Table 4.

The presence of organic acids in mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	Vegetation phase	The presence of organic acids in mulberry leaves							
		oxalic	tartaric	citric	malic	Succinic	Benzoic	Gallic	salicylic
Hasak mulberry	Blossom	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
	Fruiting	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
	Ripening of berries	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
SANIISH-34	Blossom	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-
	Fruiting	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+
	Ripening of berries	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
Jar arik -8	Blossom	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
	Fruiting	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
	Ripening of berries	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
Sha-tut mulberry	Blossom	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
	Fruiting	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Ripening of berries	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Further, substances of P-vitamin action (flavonoids and coumarins) were found in the leaves of the studied mulberry varieties. The content of flavonoids was divided into separate components. At the same time, rutin and gineroside were found in the leaves of the studied varieties, and quercin was additionally found in the shade.

The greatest amount of flavonoids is contained in leaves harvested in June. The first three varieties are similar in content of flavonoids, and there are several more of them in the leaves of the Sha-tut.

By studying the flavonoids in the leaves of the same varieties, the coumarin content was determined.

More coumarins (with some advantage in the Sha-tut variety) are found in young leaves harvested in late

April and early May. By the method of chromatographic analysis, the presence of osthol with Rf -0,66, fraxinol with Rf -0,78 was established in extracts of the leaves of Hasak, Jar Arik-8, SANIISH-34 and in the leaves of Sha-tut presumably also imperotonin with Rf -0,32.

The leaves of the studied mulberry varieties, along with other chemical components, also contain biologically active resin substances.

The isolated substances are soluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone and partially in ether, the constants of resinous substances of mulberry leaves are shown in Table.5.

Table 5.

Constants of resinous substances of mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	Constants of resinous substances of mulberry leaves			
	Acid number	Saponification number	Ethereal number	Iodine number
Hasak mulberry	60,5	112,0	51,5	40,75
Jar arik-8	60,5	111,1	46,6	40,26
SANIISH-34	61,5	111,2	50,1	34,16
Sha-tut mulberry T	61,7	112,2	50,5	40,26

The maximum accumulation of substances is observed in the leaves collected in June and July, -7.2-8.5%. The leaves of the highly fertile Sha-tut form with physico-chemical constants are richer in resin content: a specific gravity of 1.1300-1.1967 and a liquefaction temperature of 85-105 ° C.

The presence and quantity of ash elements in the studied resins were determined. The resin of the leaves of the Hasak variety contains 20, Jar arik-8– 21,

SANIISH-34– 21, Sha-tut – 23 of the following micro and macro elements:

Si, Al, Ca, K, Na, Be, Fe, Mg, P, Ba, Sr, Mn, V, Ti, Cr, Ag, Pb, Ni, Mo, Ga, Sn, Co, Zn.

The resins of the studied varieties are characterized by high antimicrobial activity manifested against pyrogenic microbes and representatives of the intestinal typhoid group. The results of studying the antimicrobial action of resins isolated from leaves are shown in Table

Table 6.

Antimicrobial effect of resins isolated from mulberry leaves

Mulberry variety	bacterium					
	Typhoid bacillus is a bacterium	Staphylococcus aureus	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	colon bacillus	plain	Dysentery stick
Hasak mulberry	Сл.	-	20	20	-	-
Jar arik-8	20	Сл.	30	24	20	24
SANIISH-34	Сл.	Сл.	20	Сл.	20	-
Sha-tut mulberry	24	Сл.	20	20	18	20

Approx. The numbers indicate the area of action; Sl. – weak action.

Recently, it has been noted that the additional addition of trace elements in the form of a weak hydrochloric acid solution to dosage forms prepared from the same raw materials increases their physiological activity.

Conclusion

Thus, when young leaves appear, there is a low content of ascorbic acid, which increases by the time of flowering and continues to accumulate, reaching a maximum by the time the berries are tied.

More coumarins (with some advantage in the Sha-tut variety) are found in young leaves harvested in late April and early May. By the method of chromatographic analysis, the presence of osthol with Rf -0.66, fraxinol with Rf -0.78 was established in the extracts of the leaves of Hasak, Jar arik-8, SANIISH-34, and in the leaves of Sha-tut presumably also imperitonin with Rf -0.32.

Substances of P-vitamin action (flavonoids and coumarins) were found in the leaves of the studied mulberry varieties, the presence of rutin and gineroside was found in the leaves of the studied varieties, and quercin was additionally found in the leaves of the studied varieties. The greatest amount of flavonoids is contained in leaves harvested in June. The first three varieties are similar in content of flavonoids, and there are several more of them in Sha leaves.

The leaves of the studied mulberry varieties, along with other chemical components, also contain biologically active resin substances. The maximum accumulation of substances is observed in leaves harvested in June and July - 7.2-8.5%. The leaves of a highly fertile form with physico-chemical constants are richer in resin content: a specific gravity of 1.1300-1.1967 and a liquefaction temperature of 85-105 ° C.

The presence and quantity of ash elements in the studied resins were determined. The resin of the leaves

of the Hasak variety contains – 20 elements, Jar arik-8 – 21 elements, SANIISH-34– 21 elements and there are 23 types of micro and macro elements in Sha-tut

As can be seen from all of the above, mulberry leaf is the most valuable source of medicinal forms for the human body. And it is not for nothing that the silkworm caterpillar, which produces such a unique product as silk, is a monophage, i.e. it feeds exclusively on mulberry leaves, receiving from it all the elements necessary for life.

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